

DEMONETIZATION AND ITS IMPACT

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Abstract

Demonetization is a big step initiated by government of India. It addresses various issues like black money, terrorism, counterfeit currency, corruption etc. Many countries have tried demonetization much before India. Demonetization affects common people in short run, however the long term benefits overcome the short term challenges. Government has taken many initiatives to curb black money like Income Declaration scheme, Black Money and Imposition of tax act, 2015 but this scheme overrides all other initiatives. It forces people to deposit or exchange their old currency with banks. The secondary data have been used for the study and the study discusses the impact of demonetization on different sectors.

Keywords: Demonetization, Terrorism, Counterfeit, Challenges, Black Money, Imposition, Exchange.

INTRODUCTION Money is the lifeblood of every economy. Human needs are unlimited. In order to achieve human wants barter system was introduced, where one can get something with the exchange of something. But the invention of money abolished the barter system and became a strong pillar to build an economy. Exchange of money facilitates ease of doing business and easy taxation. An economy is an area where production, exchange, distribution and services take place which is known as formal economy. An informal economy is one where activities are neither taxed nor monitored by government. Corruption, Terrorism, Black money, Poor governance leads to parallel economy. In order to minimize the parallel economy, government takes different steps like Demonetization, Economic liberalization etc.

On 8th November, 2016 the government of India has demonetized the high value of currency notes of Rs. 500 and 1000. The government of India has given time line to exchange the currency notes up to December 30, 2016. The government eliminates old notes from circulation with replacement of new set of notes. The major aim of demonetization is to control a counterfeit note that contributes to terrorism and to eliminate the black money.

To understand the effect of elimination of cash (Rs. 500 & 1000 notes), it is very important to understand the requirement of cash in an economy. Broadly, there are four types of transaction that take place in the economy: accounted transactions, unaccounted transactions, transactions from informal sector and illegal transactions.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

On 8 November, 2016, the government of India announced the demonetization of Rs. 500 and Rs. 1000 notes to curb the black money, counterfeit notes and to stop terrorism. The sudden announcement created cash shortage in the economy and significant disruption throughout the economy. The move was heavily criticized as poorly planned and unfair, political parties started protests, litigation and strikes. The problem of our study is to determine whether demonetization is really effective or not for the economy.

IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

The present study mainly analyses the impact of Demonetization on different sectors in India and to find out its effectiveness. GDP is one of the major indicators to measure the growth of a nation. A few studies have analyzed the history of demonetization and the concept. Though few studies have been undertaken, this study is a maiden attempt to analyze the impact of Demonetization on different sectors and economy in India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are:

- (a) To understand the conceptual framework of demonetization and its effect on different sectors of the economy.
- (b) To examine the impact of Demonetization and its possible impact on economic growth.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Sources of Data

Secondary data have been used for the study. The required data are collected from World Bank data base.

Sample Design

From literature review of Demonetization it is found that 12 countries have adopted the tool of Demonetization across the globe as of now. Out of 12 countries we have taken Australia as developed, North Korea as developing and Myanmar as under developed countries. To examine the impact of demonetization on economic growth of a country we have taken one country from each category. For economic growth we have taken GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION as indicators.

Period of the Study

For analysis of data we have taken 5 years data before demonetization and 5 years after demonetization.

Tools

Paired t test has been applied to know the impact of demonetization on economic growth. Since our study is about determining the impact on economic growth before demonetization and after demonetization, so the paired t test is a suitable statistical tool to measure the impact. Besides that it has small sample size i.e. < 30 .

Hypothesis:

- H^1_0 There is no difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of Myanmar before and after the demonetization.
 H^1_1 There is significant difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of Myanmar before and after the demonetization.
- H^2_0 There is no difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of North Korea before and after the demonetization.
 H^2_1 There is significant difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of North Korea before and after the demonetization.
- H^3_0 There is no difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of Australia before and after the demonetization.
 H^3_1 There is significant difference between GDPPC, GDP and INFLATION of Australia before and after the demonetization.

CONCEPTUAL STUDY

Demonetization is the process of devaluing a piece of currency to zero. In other words, making the value of a particular denomination of currency is nil. It is the process of removing certain form of currency from circulation. It has been done three times in the history of India, first in 1946, 1978 and then in 2016. On 8th Nov 2016, Prime Minister Mr Narendra Modi discontinued 500 and 1000 Rupee notes. Demonetization was a very bold step taken by the government and the step would surely help in building our nation, it will bring transparency in system and lead us towards a better future. The move also showed the mismanagement and lack of planning within the system, frequent change of rules by RBI, deaths of people standing in queues, shortage of newly printed notes led to sufferings of a common man but in longer it will boost the Indian economy.

Objective of Demonetization

- ❖ To eradicate black money
- ❖ To remove counterfeit currency
- ❖ To fight against terrorism
- ❖ To stop money laundering activities
- ❖ To mitigate corruption and so on
- ❖ Get every citizen in India to be monitored online
- ❖ Boost the economy
- ❖ Crack down on black political campaigning

Pros

Demonetization of currency has many pros such as,

- ❖ Menace of black money in form of cash sometimes also referred as parallel economy can be curbed
- ❖ It will lead towards digital economy
- ❖ Counterfeit currency can easily be uprooted
- ❖ Terror financing is also expected to take a hit
- ❖ Nefarious ways of election financing can be controlled
- ❖ It will serve as a push towards cashless economy
- ❖ Inflation can also be controlled up to a certain extent

Cons

In spite of the long term benefits, demonetization has some temporary back-draws,

- ❖ Growth percentage of the GDP is depreciated by 0.5 percentage

- ❖ It led to shortage of cash which resulted in insufficiency of working capital in the manufacturing sector
- ❖ It also had an adverse effect on the agricultural sector as the prices fell.
- ❖ It affects regular business transactions.

Implementation of Demonetization across the Globe and its Impact

Demonetization is not new to India or to the outside world. Across the world various governments have decided to ban currency note in circulation, declaring huge amount of cash useless overnights. This includes fighting counterfeiting, stopping terror activities, battling black money etc. Many countries have adopted this process of demonetization to eradicate black money, to overcome hyperinflation, to bring economic stability, to remove counterfeit currency etc. Some of the examples of demonetization countries around the world are:

(a) Zimbabwe

Government of Zimbabwe called for demonetization of its high value currency note with a face of one hundred trillion dollars to overcome hyperinflation. The 3-month process involved abolishing the Zimbabwean dollar from the country's financial system and freezing the US dollar, Botswana pula, and South African rand as the country's legal tender in a bid to stabilize the economy.

(b) Soviet Union

To remove black money and increase the currency value, Mikhail Gorbachev, in January 1991, withdrew 50 and 100 Ruble notes from circulation by way of demonetization. The move didn't success which resulted into a cheap attempt which brought down his authority and led to Soviet breakup

(c) Myanmar

Demonetization took place in this country many times. In 1987, Myanmar's military abolished around 80% value of money to curb black market. The decision led to economic disruption which in turn led to mass protests that killed many people.

(d) Australia

Australia became the first country to release polymer (plastic) notes to stop widespread counterfeiting. Since the purpose was to replace paper with plastic and only the material changed, it did not have any side-effects on the economy.

(e) Ghana

In 1982, Ghana ditched their 50 cedis note to tackle tax evasion and empty excess liquidity. This made the people of the country to support the black market and they started investing in physical assets which made the economy weak.

(f) Nigeria

During the government of Muhammadu Buhari in 1984, Nigeria introduced new currency and banned the old notes. However, the debt-ridden and inflation hit country did not take the change well

(g) Pakistan

From December 2016, Pakistan eradicated the old notes as it will bring in new designs. Pakistan legally issued the tender a year and a half back, and therefore, the citizens had time to exchange the old notes and get newly designed notes.

(h) North Korea

The demonetization that happened in North Korea in 2010 left people with no food and shelter. Kim-Jong Il introduced a reform that knocked off two zeros from the face value of the old currency in order to banish black market.

(i) European Union

European Union adopted euro in 2002, the authorities fixed exchange rates for the national currencies into euros. The old currency remained convertible into euros, so that economy would run smoothly.

(j) United States of America

In 1946, the U.S.A stopped printing of \$1000 and larger denominations of currency and produced \$ 100 denomination of currency.

(k) Philippines

In 2015, the country demonetized notes which had been in circulation for 30 years with new ones which had only been in circulation since 2010 to prevent counterfeiting. From January 2017 onward, the old bills will be demonetized.

(l) United Kingdom

UK has demonetized 1 pound coin in 2016 to counterfeit the fake coins. The country circulates new pound coins developed with new features.

IMPACT OF DEMONETIZATION

Cash is to be preferred as the best mode for transaction globally. In some developed countries, transactions carried out through cash are less than 50% of total transactions. In India, this ratio stands at around 95%. Easy accessibility, certainty of

acceptance and no additional charges makes it universally acceptable.

Black Money Hoarders

The main reason behind this demonetization is to eradicate black money. With this move of government, black money holders either have to show their income source from which they earned their black money to the department or to burn the stored income. However people declaring their income in excess of threshold limit will be subjected to scrutiny.

Fake Note Circuits

Terrorism is a frightening thing and has been running their operations using fake currency notes. Hence withdrawing the entire series of high-value currency notes and introducing new currency definitely affect on terrorism.

Rural Economy

People in rural India who have Rs.1000 and Rs.500 notes, but no social form of identification will have a tough time in exchanging their notes. Most of the rural population does not have even any idea of banking. Hence this is likely to be a huge impact for such sections.

Domestic/Household Sector

The aim of demonetization is to curb the use of these high value notes in the black money market. Now almost everyone has Rs1000/500 notes so now it would become difficult for the common people to do their business works easily.

Bank Deposits

Demonetization of old notes will boost bank deposits, this will increase bank's deposits by a huge margin and this will increase their lending activities.

Impact on Jewellery and Real Estate Business

The decision of government has been welcomed by the jewellery industry as demand for gold will rise and people will have more faith in gold than the currency notes. Hence it is expected to benefit the industry.

Cashless Economy

As we know cash withdrawals limit from ATM and Banks is being restricted, this will lead to payment mechanism through online or card payment. Card transactions will slowly replace the cash transaction in daily activities.

Impact on economy

- Fiscal deficit will come down
- Currency to become stronger
- Industry will become more productive
- Inflation will come down as housing prices will drop and food inflation will come down
- Tax rates will come down as more people will be in tax net
- Business will be able to borrow at cheaper rates
- FDI to sky rocket

(a) Effect on parallel economy

The removal of these 500 and 1000 notes and replacement of the same with new 500 and 2000 Rupee Notes is expected to

- Remove black money from the economy as they will be blocked since the owners will not be in a position to deposit the same in the banks,
- Temporarily stall the circulation of large volume of counterfeit currency
- Curb the funding for anti-social elements like smuggling, terrorism, etc.

(b) Effect on Money Supply

With the older 500 and 1000 Rupees notes being discarded, until the new 500 and 2000 Rupees notes get widely circulated in the market, money supply is expected to reduce in the short run.

(c) Effect on Demand

The overall demand is expected to be affected to an extent. The demand in following areas is to be impacted particularly:

- Consumer goods
- Real Estate and Property
- Gold and luxury goods
- Automobiles (up to a certain limit)

(d) Effect on Prices

Price level is expected to be lowered due to moderation from demand side. This demand driven fall in prices:

- Consumer goods: Prices are expected to fall only marginally due to moderation in

demand as use of cards and cheques would compensate for some purchases.

- Real Estate and Property: Prices in this sector are expected to fall, because major part of cash is required for sales.

(e) Effect on various economic entities

With the lowering of cash transaction in the short run, the society could face sort term disruptions until the new notes are spread widely into circulation. These sections are:

- Agriculture and related sector
- Small traders
- SME
- Services Sector
- Households
- Political Parties
- Professionals like doctor, carpenter, utility service providers, etc.
- Retail outlets

The nature, frequency and amounts of the commercial transactions involved with these sections of the economy necessitate cash transactions on more frequently. Thus, these segments are expected to have the most significant impact post this demonetization process and the introduction of new notes in circulation.

(f) Effect on GDP

With the reduction of demand the GDP could be impacted. However with the recent rise in festival demand is expected to offset this fall in overall impact. Moreover, the negative impact on GDP may vanish once the cash situation becomes normal.

(g) Effect on Banks

As directed by the Government, the 500 and 1000 Rupee notes eliminated which are to be deposited or exchanged in banks. This will lead to more amounts being deposited in Savings and Current Account of commercial banks. This in turn will enhance the liquidity position of the banks, which can be utilized further for lending purposes.

DATA ANALYSIS & IMPACT STUDY

Table No - 1
Paired t Test Table Determining Demonetization Impact (Myanmar)

Table Value at 5% level of significance for 4 d.f	Test value		
	GDPPC	GDP	INFLATION
2.776	-0.53	-0.27	0.10

Source: Self Compiled

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

Here in the given table we have calculated t value i.e.-0.53. At 5% level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom, the critical value of t is 2.776. Since calculated value is less than critical value, so null hypothesis is accepted. It indicates there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDPPC.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

The above table shows t value is.-0.27. The critical value is 2,776 at 5% level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. It denotes that calculated value is less than the critical value, so null hypothesis is accepted. Hence there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDP.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

Here our t value is 0.10. Since the calculated value of t < the critical value with 4 d.f at 5% level of significance, so we accept the null hypothesis H₀ and conclude that there is no significant impact of demonetization on INFLATION.

Table No - 2
Paired t Test Table Determining Demonetization Impact (North Korea)

Table Value at 5% level of significance for 4 d.f	Test value		
	GDPPC	GDP	INFLATION
2.776	0.53	1.80	0.35

Source: Self Compiled

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

From above table it is found that calculated t value is 0.53 whereas the critical value is 2.776 at 5% level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. Here we find that calculated value is less than critical value, so null hypothesis is accepted. It concludes that there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDPPC.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

Looking up the table one can find the value of t is 1.80 which is less than critical value i.e. 2.776 for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance. Since calculated value is less than critical value, so null hypothesis H₀ is accepted and we can draw conclusion that there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDP.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

The calculated t value is 0.35. We found out critical value of t at 5% level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom is 2.776. Here calculated value is less than critical value, so null hypothesis H₀ is accepted. Thus there is no significant impact of demonetization on INFLATION.

Table No - 3
Paired t Test Table Determining Demonetization Impact (Australia)

Table Value at 5% level of significance for 4 d.f	Test value		
	GDPPC	GDP	INFLATION
2.776	1.08	0.36	0.007

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDPPC before demonetization and after demonetization.

We have calculated t value i.e.1.08. The critical value of t is 2.776 at 5% level of significance for 4 degrees of freedom. Here null hypothesis is accepted because calculated value is less than critical value. Hence it is proved there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDPPC.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between GDP before demonetization and after demonetization.

The calculated t value is 0.36 however critical value is 2,776 for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance. We accept null hypothesis H₀ as calculated value is less than critical value. Therefore there is no significant impact of demonetization on GDP.

H₀: There is no significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

H₁: There is significant relationship between INFLATION before demonetization and after demonetization.

Table no 3 shows that the calculated value of t is 0.007. The critical value is 2.776 at 5% level of significance with 4 degree of freedom. The calculated value is less than the critical value. Hence we conclude null hypothesis is accepted i.e. there is no significant impact of demonetization on INFLATION.

FINDINGS

- ❖ It affects drastically to black money holders, counterfeit currency and terrorism.
- ❖ Demonetization will get a boost for banks as it strengthens their liquidity position which ultimately leads to Digitalization.
- ❖ It helps to track tax avoiders as they will deposit their money with bank, so government will keep a track of it and trap those.
- ❖ From the analysis of data regarding the impact of Demonetization on economic indicators such as GDPPC, GDP & INFLATION; Demonetization has no significant impact on economic growth.

CONCLUSION

Demonetization is like two faces of a coin because one side it will benefit the nation and other side it's going to create some temporary problems. The demonetization undertaken by government is a shock to the economy. It mitigates the problems of black money and counterfeit notes. Demonetization is simultaneously followed by remonetization. The government of India has introduced new notes of Rs. 2000 and Rs. 500 denomination with the elimination of old notes. It leads to cash less economy which influences e-banking and e-commerce. Demonetization will help the e-commerce industry and encourage the people to use more cash less transactions in day to day life, so that people need not carry any cash for any purchases. It will help the banking sector to expand their business throughout the globe. There are many countries that tried demonetization before. Some countries get success and some failure. Success or failure depends on the behavior of government policies and mindset of people.

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